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Work Package WP11

JRA2 – Improved and Extended Real-Time/Co-simulation and HIL Tools

Deliverable D11.2

D-JRA2.2 Software Release

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List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
API	Application Programming Interface
CIDR	Classless Inter-Domain Routing
CR	Custom Resource
CRD	Custom Resource Definition
FMI	Functional Mockup Interface
FMU	Functional Mockup Unit
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
IaaS	Infrastructure as Code
ICE	Interactive Connectivity Establishment
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IP	Internet Protocol
IT	Information Technologies
JRA	Joint Research Activity
LV	Low Voltage
NAT	Network Address Translation
PoC	Proof of Concept
POSIX	Portable Operating System Interface
RI	Research Infrastructure
RaaS	Research Infrastructure as Code
RT	Real Time
STL	Same Time Loop
STUN	Session Traversal Utilities for NAT
TC	Traffic Control
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TURN	Traversal Using Relays around NAT
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
VPN	Virtual Private Network
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language

Executive Summary

The Joint Research Activity 2 focused on interconnecting and integrating Research Infrastructures in the form of simulators and physical laboratory equipment. The work specifically addressed multi-domain co-simulation, mixed continuous and event-based co-simulation, hardware-in-the-loop testing, virtual interconnections of multiple physical laboratories, and virtual interconnections of multiple real-time simulators.

This document covers those results of Joint Research Activity 2 that are available in machine-readable form, i.e., simulation models, code examples, Proof of Concept and deployable tools. It is meant to be used alongside the previous Deliverable D11.1 “D-JRA2.1 Coupling Methods” which covers methodical and technical background information. This document primarily focuses on implementation considerations while providing technical background.

The software releases covered in this document are a Proof of Concept implementation of an event-based co-simulation of electrical and communication networks, an implementation of a multi-energy network co-simulation using same time loops, a framework to accelerate geographically distributed experiments, a tool for the automatic establishment of peer-to-peer overlay networks across firewalls and organisational boundaries, and a network emulator for Kubernetes pods.

Several of the software releases in this document will be used in the demonstration activities of ERIGrid 2.0 and are being developed further. Therefore, this document is only a snapshot of the results.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

The Joint Research Activity (JRA) 2 covers a broad range of different but related topics, with a common focus on the interconnection and integration of Research Infrastructures (RIs) in the form of simulators as well as physical laboratory equipment, as depicted in Figure 1. In tasks JRA 2.1 “Multi-domain Co-simulation” and JRA 2.2 “Real-time Coupling and Hardware-in-the-Loop Approaches”, this is applied to:

- Multi-domain co-simulation,
- Mixed continuous and event-based co-simulation,
- Local and remote hardware-in-the-loop testing,
- Virtual interconnections of multiple physical laboratories, and
- Virtual interconnections of multiple real-time simulators.

This report provides instructions and documentation for software and other machine-consumable results of ERIGrid 2.0’s JRA 2.1 and JRA 2.2 activities. This includes simulation models, code examples serving as a Proof of Concept (PoC) as well as deployable tools. This document does not detail the methodical and technical background behind these results in order to avoid repeating the content of Deliverable D11.1 (*D-JRA2.1 Coupling Methods, 2023*); it should therefore be used in conjunction with the former. Where the technical background is provided in the document at hand, it will primarily cover implementation considerations.

Figure 1: Possible coupling modes between Research Infrastructures (highlighted in green are the modes which are the primary focus of this report; dashed red lines denote possible modes not covered here).

1.2 Structure of the Document

The remainder of this document is organised as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the software developments available from JRA 2 and their relation to the areas of work (work tracks) covered. Section 3 holds the main content of this report, with subsections dedicated to the description of each software release. Finally, a short summary of the main findings/outcomes is provided in Section 4.

2 Overview of Software Developments

As an outcome of different work tracks in the JRA 2 and the related developments, the following sections give a brief overview of the available software packages.

2.1 Work Tracks

The work in JRA 2 has been categorised into eight distinct work tracks, consisting of three tracks in JRA 2.1 and five tracks in JRA 2.2. The structure is as follows:

Track 1.1: Co-simulation of Alternating Current (AC) grids and Information Technologies (IT) networks

Track 1.2: Co-simulation of AC grids and heat networks

Track 1.3: Co-simulation initialisation

Track 2.1: Time delay compensation and bandwidth estimation

Track 2.2: Improving stability of Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) simulation

Track 2.3: Sensitivity analysis based on mathematical modelling

Track 2.4: Applicability of different Real Time (RT) methods for validation

Track 2.5: Accelerating time-to-experiment for remote RI coupling

The content and background of these tracks are described in detail in Deliverable D11.1 (*D-JRA2.1 Coupling Methods*, 2023). The following section provides an overview of the software releases covered in the deliverable at hand and their relation to these work tracks.

2.2 Software Packages

The following list provides an overview of the different software packages which have been realised in ERIGrid 2.0 so far; the detailed description as well as the link to the code is provided in Section 3:

AC-ICT Co-simulation PoC: This release contains a PoC implementation of an event-based co-simulation of electrical and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) networks compliant with the Functional Mockup Interface (FMI) 3.0 standard¹ and using Mosaik 3.0² as a co-simulation master. The implementation consists of several Python-based components (pandapower³ as a network simulator as well as a custom controller) and a custom network simulator written in C++ and is a direct outcome of Track 1.1. The release is described in Section 3.1.

Superdense Time Benchmark: This release contains an extended implementation of the multi-energy network benchmark, which was developed in JRA 1 and documented in Deliverable D10.1 (*D-JRA1.1 Benchmark Scenarios*, 2022). The benchmark contains components of the electricity and the heating system, which causes the initialisation to be challenging and time-consuming. It was adapted in Track 1.3 to use a Same Time Loop (STL)

¹<https://fmi-standard.org/docs/3.0>

²<https://mosaik.offis.de>

³<http://www.pandapower.org>

to speed up the initialisation (van der Meer, Schwarz, & Heussen, 2022). The release is described in Section 3.2

RlasC Platform: This software package contains Research Infrastructure as Code (RlasC), a framework to accelerate distributed RI experiments inspired by the Infrastructure as Code (IaC) paradigm (Quattrocchi & Tamburri, 2023). It enables the automation of common tasks related to the deployment of multi-RI experiments, using definition files to control, among others, the deployment of controllers and other software and the setup of network connections across heterogeneous environments. RlasC is primarily a result of Track 2.5, with contributions from Track 2.1. The release is described in Section 3.3

cunicu Package: This release contains cunicu⁴, a user-space daemon establishing a mesh of peer-to-peer Virtual Private Network (VPN) connections across firewalls and organisational boundaries, automating the selection of appropriate connection strategies and fallback methods. In the ERIGrid 2.0 context, cunicu enables the rapid interconnection of RIs for geographically distributed experiments, using existing communication solutions designed for local area networks. cunicu is primarily a result of Track 2.5. The release is described in Section 3.4

k8s-netem Package: It provides traffic control, i.e., a means to programmatically change the properties of a network interface, to Kubernetes pods⁵. Its primary purpose is the emulation of degraded network connections which may exhibit, e.g., increased latency, jitter or packet error rate. The package simplifies automated deployments in dynamic environments by automatically associating and disassociating Kubernetes pods and traffic control profiles. k8s-netem is primarily a result of Track 2.5. The release is described in Section 3.5

⁴<https://cunicu.li>

⁵<https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/workloads/pods>

3 Available Software Releases

In the following section, available software releases related to the work in JRA 2 are outlined. The latest developments (incl. related documentation) of those software packages are generally provided in an open source/open access way at ERIGrid 2.0's GitHub page⁶ and Zenodo Community⁷.

3.1 AC-ICT Co-simulation PoC

Motivation

Co-simulations of AC power systems and digital communication networks are challenging due to their different time bases. Power systems are modelled as continuous-time systems, while networks are modelled as discrete, event-driven systems. The FMI standard was adopted to provide a universal way of coupling existing simulation tools by either exchanging entire simulation models with a central solver or by continuously exchanging state information of running simulators. However, the earlier version of the standard (i.e., FMI 2.0) had limitations in handling advanced co-simulation issues, especially in event handling between different types of models. To address these limitations, the FMI 3.0 standard (Junghanns et al., 2021) was developed with advanced features able to bridge the gap between continuous-time models and other types of models, improving the co-simulation between systems with different time bases.

A main goal of work Track 1.1 has been to demonstrate the coupling of multiple FMI 3.0-compatible Functional Mockup Units (FMUs)⁸ using Mosaik 3.0 as a co-simulation master. As part of the 3.0 release, Mosaik has gained a more flexible concept of internal time, allowing it to be used to orchestrate co-simulations where simulators do not advance in regular time steps.

Functionality

The implementation bridges two different simulator stepping paradigms which exist between FMI 3.0 and the simulator Application Programming Interface (API) of Mosaik 3.0. FMI 3.0-compatible FMUs expect the end of the last successful step (i.e., `currentCommunicationPoint`) and the maximum permissible step (i.e., `communicationStepSize`) as arguments to a stepping request. The Mosaik 3.0 API on the other hand provides a minimum permissible step target (i.e., `t`) and a maximum permissible step (i.e., `max_advance`). Transforming between the two is not entirely straightforward, and several corner cases exist – for example regarding the first step after simulator initialisation and steps of length zero. These issues have been addressed as part of a Python-based simulator wrapper.

The code release consists of several independent scenarios which make use of the same FMUs. The primary scenario is identical to the one described in Deliverable D11.1 (*D-JRA2.1 Coupling Methods*, 2023); voltage regulation in a power grid with two Low Voltage (LV) radials is provided by a tap-changing transformer upstream. A tap changer controller receives sampled voltage measurements at certain intervals and sends up/down actuation commands to the tap changer. The communication link between the voltage measurement and the tap changer

⁶<https://github.com/ERIGrid2>

⁷<https://zenodo.org/communities/erigrd2>

⁸An abstract representation of a dynamic system based on a tool independent standard interface using FMI.

controller is explicitly modelled as a communication simulator which allows the performance of the link to be adjusted. Figure 2 provides an overview of this setup.

Figure 2: Overview of co-simulation test setup based on Mosaik 3.0.

A second scenario has been created as a variation of the above to serve the needs of JRA 1.2 “Uncertainty Representation and Validation Methods”; here, voltage regulation is provided by a flexible load instead of the tap changer. Both scenarios combine the following types of simulators as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Types of simulators used for implemented co-simulation scenario.

Function	Simulator Name	Type of Implementation
Electrical network simulator	pandapower	FMI 2.0 FMU generated by pythonfmu
Sampling voltage measurement	periodic_sender	Mosaik-component written in Python
Communication network	pipeline_cfg	FMI 3.0 FMU written in C++
Tap changer controller	tap_controller	FMI 2.0 FMU generated by pythonfmu
Data logger	collector	Mosaik-component written in Python

Code Overview

The entire codebase can be found at the related projects’ GitHub page⁹. The simulation consists of three types of building blocks:

- FMI 3.0-compliant FMUs written natively in C++; these can be found in the `fmi3` folder.
- FMI 2.0-compliant FMUs written in Python and compiled to C before execution; these are contained in the `python` folder which is again divided into subfolders for the individual simulation scenarios.
- Native Python code emulating FMUs (i.e., FMI 2.0 or 3.0 compliant); these reside in the scenario-specific subfolders of the `python` folder as well.
- Python classes belonging to the simulation framework, they can be also found in the `python` folder.

Usage Instructions

Before the simulation can be run, the FMUs have to be compiled. Currently, the correct compilation has only been tested on several Linux platforms, although other Portable Operating

⁹<https://github.com/ERIGrid2/JRA2.1.1-PoC>

System Interface (POSIX) or POSIX-emulating platforms such as Windows may work as well. The build system for the native C++ FMUs expects the following packages and tools to be installed:

- `cmake`, for generating platform-dependent autotools build scripts,
- `autotools` (`autoconf`, `automake` etc.), and
- `g++`, i.e., the C++ variant of `gcc`.

The compilation is started with the provided script `build_c_fmus.sh`. Compiling the Python-based FMUs additionally requires:

- `python` \geq 3.9 (earlier versions have not been tested), and
- `pythonfmu` \geq 0.6.2, for generating C FMUs from Python-based simulators (`pandapower`, etc.).

The Python FMUs are compiled using the script `build_python_fmus.sh`. It should be ensured that the Python version used to compile the FMUs is identical to the one used to run the simulation later. A version mismatch will likely cause the execution of the simulation to fail. This is relevant when compiling inside virtual environments, or when compiling and executing on different machines. After a successful compilation, all FMUs can be found in the `fmus` folder which is generated by the compilation scripts if it does not exist.

The following Python packages are required to run the simulation:

- `FMPy` \geq 0.3.15 in order to generate native Python FMUs,
- `mosaik` 3.0 as a co-simulation master,
- `pandapower`, provides the electrical loadflow,
- `numpy`, used by the electrical network calculation,
- `pandas`, currently in use by the collector class for data storage and serialisation, and
- `matplotlib` for visualisation (presently disabled, but the dependency remains for later use).

Currently, two scenarios are provided as examples and/or proof-of-concept:

1. `run_test_scenario.sh` simulates, and
2. `run_jra12_scenario.sh`.

The codebase is still under active development due to its central role in the demonstration activities that take place later in the project. Additional scenarios will be added and updated usage information will be provided in the `README` file at the related projects' GitHub page¹⁰.

3.2 Superdense Time Benchmark

Motivation

Work Track 1.3 addressed challenges with the initialisation of co-simulation setups for integrated energy systems. One aspect of initialisation in co-simulation is to achieve a coherent

¹⁰<https://github.com/ERIGrid2/JRA2.1.1-PoC/blob/main/README.md>

initial state across the sub-models in a co-simulation scenario. If dependencies are distributed over multiple models, this usually causes cyclic dependencies, which have to be handled. Two common ways of handling them are either to split up the cyclic dependencies by shifting the returning dependency to the next time step or to allow STLs to iterate multiple times without increasing the simulation time (see Figure 3).

As an example, the co-simulation framework Mosaik was used together with the multi-energy benchmark as it is described in Deliverable D10.1 (*D-JRA1.1 Benchmark Scenarios*, 2022) and on the projects' Zenodo Community (*ERIGrid2/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks: v1.0*, 2021). STLs in Mosaik were introduced as a new feature together with improved event-based simulation capabilities in version 3.0 (Ofenloch et al., 2022). Thus, the cyclic dependencies, which were previously solved by shifting the returning connection, could be changed to STLs to investigate the differences between these two methods as published in (van der Meer et al., 2022).

Figure 3: Visualisation of superdense time (i.e., same time loops) in Mosaik (Raub et al., 2021).

Functionality

The scenario extends the multi-energy benchmark with a STL for improved initialisation of the simulation models. The initial multi-energy benchmark was based on fixed discrete steps, which require some initialisation time until the simulation models reach a stable state. Therefore, an extra day had to be simulated for each scenario, just to be discarded later because it was not needed for the analysis of the results. With the STL, this initialisation phase was drastically reduced, as the simulation components can do multiple loops within the same time step without increasing simulation time (see Figure 4). Thus, the simulation just started after a stable state of simulation models was found in the STL. As can be seen in Figure 4, during the STL the temperatures in different zones of the hot water tank are diverging, (see Figure 4c, and Figure 4d) and the normal heat pump behaviour is starting earlier than in the simulation run without the STL (see Figure 4a and Figure 4b).

Code Overview

As described in the documentation of Mosaik¹¹, cyclic dependencies have to be connected by one *weak* connection. To enter and stay in the STL, the simulator has to provide the according attribute(s) via the `get_data` function with the current step time as output time. Thus, the simulator had to be slightly updated. Additionally, some new logic had to be implemented to decide when the STL can be left again. For that, in the flex heat control and the district heating

¹¹<https://mosaik.readthedocs.io/en/latest/scheduler.html#same-time-algebraic-loops>

Figure 4: Comparison of electrical consumption and tank temperatures of one-day simulation with and without STL.

network simulator, some code was added to compare the delta of the current value of attributes to their value from the previous step and leave the STL if a stable state was reached.

As the STL feature was quite new to Mosaik, some fixes and extensions of Mosaik were applied during the implementation of the example scenario, which found their way into the newest Mosaik releases up to version 3.1.1. One last problem for the execution of the STL example scenario, is the limitation of having only one weak connection per cycle. It is currently under discussion to lift this restriction, as described in Mosaik issue 151 in GitLab¹². As the change is not yet part of a Mosaik release, the scenario will rely on the corresponding branch of the Mosaik repository until it is published. The described scenario is available at the related projects' GitHub page¹³.

Usage Instructions

All required Python dependencies can be found in the `requirements.txt` file. It is possible to install all dependencies at once with the following command:

```
python -m pip install -r requirements.txt
```

The benchmark simulation with voltage control *enabled* can be run using the following command:

```
python benchmark_multi_energy_sim.py --outfile benchmark_results_ctrl_enabled.h5
```

The benchmark simulation with voltage control *disabled* can be run using the following command:

¹²<https://gitlab.com/mosaik/mosaik/-/issues/151>

¹³<https://github.com/ERIGrid2/JRA-2.1.3-STL>

```
python benchmark_multi_energy_sim.py --outfile  
↳ benchmark_results_ctrl_disabled.h5 --voltage-control-disabled
```

On a typical laptop, each simulation will take about 15 minutes to complete. This can be accelerated by increasing the simulation step size or shortening the simulation period. More options can be found in the built-in usage instructions:

```
python benchmark_multi_energy_sim.py --help
```

During the initial phase, the simulation is still affected by artifacts resulting from the initial conditions. In rare cases, this causes unrealistic conditions, which may result in warnings about a lack of convergence. This is to be expected during the first few simulated hours and can be safely ignored (for this reason, the first simulated day is not taken into account in the analysis).

After running the simulations, plots which analyse the benchmark results can be produced using the following command¹⁴:

```
python benchmark_multi_energy_analysis.py
```

3.3 RlasC Platform

Motivation

RlasC, an acronym for Research Infrastructure as Code, is a framework to accelerate distributed RI experiments. RlasC is composed of several tools and services which can also be used and developed independently.

IaC refers to the practice of managing and provisioning computer data centres using machine-readable definition files instead of traditional methods like configuring physical hardware or interactive tools. This process encompasses the management of both physical components such as bare-metal servers and virtual machines, along with their respective configuration resources. These definitions are often stored in a version control system. IaC can be implemented through scripts or declarative definitions, although the term is commonly associated with promoting declarative approaches for infrastructure management. Therefore, RlasC realises the goals of IaC by utilising existing cloud computing technologies and applying them in a research environment.

Functionality

RlasC provides the following functionalities to accelerate distributed RI experiments:

- *Provisioning of Mobile Units*: A mobile unit in RlasC terminology is a gateway between local laboratory equipment and remote laboratories. The setup and maintenance updates of the units are handled by RlasC.

¹⁴Note: To exclude simulation data affected by initialisation artifacts, data from the first simulated day is not included in the analysis by default.

- *Deployment of containerised Software Components*: The mobile units join a Kubernetes cluster¹⁵ which allows a declarative description of the deployment of containerised applications.
- *Transparent Inter-laboratory Overlay Network*: RlasC simplifies the setup of distributed experiments spanning multiple laboratories by providing a transparent Internet Protocol (IP) overlay network between all participating laboratories.
- *Time Synchronisation*: For geographically distributed coupled subsystems, a common time base is required in order to synchronise the execution of experiments as well as the proper temporal alignment of simulation results (e.g., log merging). A time-synchronisation service provides this common time base by synchronising the clock of each mobile unit via one of the supported synchronisation sources.
- *Network Emulation*: Network emulation allows for a realistic emulation of real-world network characteristics. RlasC provides a network emulation service which allows the researcher to declaratively describe desired network parameters such as communication delay, packet loss, throughput, etc.

Code Overview

RlasC, together with several sub-projects, has been published open source under the Apache 2.0 license. The code base is available at the related project's GitHub page¹⁶. In addition, RlasC also has a separate website¹⁷ for better visibility to the research community.

Usage Instructions

Each RlasC agent node can be configured by a YAML Ain't Markup Language (YAML) configuration file. This configuration file is used by the agent node to register itself in the RlasC cloud. The latest edition of the example configuration listed below can be found at the projects' related GitHub page¹⁸.

```

1 # RlasC configuration file
2
3 # A unique hostname to identify the node
4 hostname: riasc-agent # changeme!
5
6 ansible:
7 # List of PGP keys which are used to verify the commits in the Ansible repo
8 keys:
9 - 09BE3BAE8D55D4CD8579285A9675EAC34897E6E2 # Steffen Vogel (RWTH)
10
11 keyserver: keys.openpgp.org
12
13 # A repository containing ansible playbooks which will be fetched via ansible-pull
14 url: https://github.com/erigrd2/riasc-ansible.git
15
16 verify_commit: true
17
18 # The playbook which should be provision the node

```

¹⁵<https://kubernetes.io>

¹⁶<https://github.com/orgs/ERIGrid2/teams/riasc/repositories>

¹⁷<https://riasc.eu>

¹⁸<https://github.com/ERIGrid2/riasc-provisioning/blob/master/common/riasc.yaml>

```

19  playbook: site.yml
20
21  # A path to the Ansible inventory within the repo from above
22  inventory: inventory/erigrd/hosts.yml
23
24  # extra_args:
25  # - --only-if-changed
26
27  # Additional variables which are passed to the Ansible playbook for provisioning
28  variables:
29  # A list of SSH keys which will be added to the 'pi' user
30  additional_ssh_keys:
31  - ssh-rsa AAAAB3NzaC1yc2EAAAADAQABAAQAC9kuBu/eYcN1hNNIWEVfsw0/r0oE1JVQPK+92Y6r856xrdaC
    ↪ pG0tHv5MBm07OfmGEFZ86e2QC0Ij5zqlwqTTNwWAHxT6H9d3CytThx54Uron0CeQxQBYcJpLDSdY5MuseZjm
    ↪ ORlW+7aSNvnUttDBYGBocl+VWaaNF+dN2MWzrGIwOrvKJ240VhPmm91Vw0IoCJkKJ9AL10EIpCH7n7jcaJYV
    ↪ BP2j+RVYfq47W4e9SfE/QlL+QVk360w+kFSeTybaMnsWALZNwk/kywzPq1dpw+4ToD6qBF61eY7ivD/ZsFpp
    ↪ bndyzjW93P03Iw1TXmFd/UK/3xzihuZE9KW10D105hny3o0DXkWK96xSFA4hhMqkVw0bNS9+jVq3fuaGNat0
    ↪ UEGOrfCPPf0fwnPYq9p0yDUViGHDhMY/yWBSqlN+L3Rt9b8hwhObhsAQiWF5ujIo3mivFD6BQQAYK52Qz778
    ↪ VRPK39kOgpYxqltcJEfjJ832arvN09XseUKUQAi50gVyXfxD3yQK++0U1E9isF+VyLd1m5MgrrtP1P20Ab2PJ
    ↪ D6UUAmpr1rEldP9jVsGpVowntC/HP4/ljCeppize4CRgZjWDHE+Yj+TwmVeuUTObniVWpE/eiQoDie+FBWPe
    ↪ Stq3UMPW5viUafzf2sCUxMyc/ZTUqy8wzDZEyfJ70GaoxPrQ==
    ↪ svogel2@eonerc.rwth-aachen.de
32
33  # Set this to true if you want to login via SSH keys only.
34  # If you dont have an SSH key, set this to false.
35  # Important: Dont forget to change the default password after your first login!
36  disable_password_login: false
37
38  # The URL of a K3S master provided by your RIAsC provider
39  server: https://k3s.riasc.eu/
40
41  labels:
42  riasc.eu/provisioned: "true"
43  topology.kubernetes.io/region: de-rwth-acs
44  riasc.eu/time-sync: ntp
45
46  # Replace this token with the token provided by your RIAsC provider
47  token: XXXXX # changeme!

```

The installation of a RIAsC node requires a working internet connection. After placing the configuration file in the current working directory, the installation (on Linux) can be started as follows:

```

$ sudo -s curl -q https://raw.githubusercontent.com/ERIGrid2/riasc-provisioning/
↪ master/common/riasc-update.sh | bash

```

After provisioning completes, the first boot may take several minutes. If the installation has been successful, the console will print the RIAsC update completed successfully! message. The RIAsC node is now ready for the deployment of services. Several services can be deployed using the Helm charts¹⁹ found at the related project's GitHub page²⁰.

Currently provided are charts for the following services:

- kilo, a multi-cloud network overlay built on WireGuard²¹ and designed for Kubernetes,

¹⁹<https://helm.sh>

²⁰<https://github.com/ERIGrid2/charts>

²¹<https://www.wireguard.com>

- `multus`, an IP gateway allowing communication with devices and services beyond a Kubernetes pod,
- `netem`, network emulation and traffic control profiles for cross-pod communication using `k8s-netem` (see Section 3.5), and
- `riasc`, an example of a multi-service node using `kilo`, `multus`, `netem`, and a Villas node.

The latest RlasC documentation can be found at the related web page²².

3.4 cunicu Package

Motivation

`cunicu` is a user-space daemon designed to manage WireGuard™ interfaces and establish peer-to-peer VPN connections in challenging network environments. It utilises a signalling layer to automate the configuration of networking links by exchanging peer information like encryption keys, hostnames, advertised networks, and reachability details. By doing so, `cunicu` eliminates the need for manual configuration and aims to be simple and user-friendly like the WireGuard project.

These features make `cunicu` suitable for quickly building multi-agent systems or connecting field devices, such as power grid monitoring infrastructure, into a fully connected mesh. In ERI-Grid 2.0, `cunicu` is being utilised to interconnect smart grid laboratories for the geographically distributed simulation of energy systems.

Functionality

From a user perspective, `cunicu` alleviates the need for manual configuration such as the exchange of public keys, IP addresses and endpoints. Thanks to Interactive Connectivity Establishment (ICE), `cunicu` is capable to establish direct connections between peers which are located behind Network Address Translation (NAT) firewalls such as home routers. In situations where ICE fails, or direct User Datagram Protocol (UDP) connectivity is not available, `cunicu` falls back to using Traversal Using Relays around NAT (TURN) relays to reroute traffic over an intermediate hop or encapsulate the WireGuard traffic via TURN Transmission Control Protocol (TCP).

Code Overview

The entire `cunicu` codebase can be found at the related project's GitHub page²³.

The implementation relies on the `pion/ice` package for ICE and bundles the Go user-space implementation of WireGuard in a single binary for systems in which WireGuard kernel support is not available yet.

²²<https://riasc.eu/docs>

²³<https://github.com/ERIGrid2/cunicu>

Usage Instructions

In order to install cunicu, a working Go environment is required. cunicu must be installed separately on each host of the desired VPN. Installation from the source is performed by running the installer:

```
$ go install github.com/stv0g/cunicu/cmd/cunicu@latest
```

The installer will fetch the required dependencies and cache them, and validate the configuration. It will then compile cunicu and place it in

```
$GOPATH/bin/cunicu
```

After configuring the WireGuard interfaces using `wg`, `wg-quick`, or `NetworkManager`, the cunicu daemon can be started:

```
sudo cunicu daemon
```

Currently, the creation of WireGuard keys, their exchange between the hosts as well as peer discovery are not automated yet. These steps have to be performed manually before starting the daemon.

After all distributed cunicu daemons have been started, they will attempt to discover valid endpoint addresses using the ICE protocol (for example by contacting Session Traversal Utilities for NAT (STUN) servers). These ICE candidates are then exchanged via the signalling server. cunicu will update the endpoint addresses of the WireGuard peers accordingly. Upon successfully establishing a connection, cunicu will write `state=connected` to the log files.

Further documentation, configuration information and the full command-line interface to the daemon can be found at the related web page²⁴.

3.5 k8s-netem Package

Motivation

k8s-netem adds support for traffic control in Kubernetes (“k8s”) pods. It allows the user to configure one or more traffic profiles to impair network traffic between pods in the cluster and between pods and external networks. This is useful in a variety of experimental settings, for example, to determine the robustness of a distributed control algorithm to network degradation or communication failure.

The traffic profiles are implemented as a Custom Resource Definition (CRD) which the user can add and modify in the Kubernetes database using standard tools like `kubectl` or the Kubernetes web interface.

The traffic profile Custom Resource (CR) is inspired by the Kubernetes `NetworkPolicy` CR and has been extended to accommodate the traffic control parameters as well as additional filters for ether types and protocols.

²⁴<https://cunicu.li/docs>

Functionality

k8s-netem traffic profiles can use a `spec.podSelector` or Classless Inter-Domain Routing (CIDR) specification to match a set of source and destination pods/networks for which the impairment should be configured. It is possible to assign multiple traffic profiles to each pod.

In addition, the impairment can be restricted to a set of UDP or TCP port numbers, ether types and IP protocols. k8s-netem continuously monitors for new or modified traffic profiles and/or pods and will update the traffic control configuration appropriately. Traffic flows across pods are supported as well as from or to specific external CIDRs.

Code Overview

The entire k8s-netem codebase can be found at the projects' related GitHub page²⁵.

k8s-netem requires the Linux kernel modules `ifb`, `sch_netem`, and `nf_tables` to be available, as well as the `nft` system utility (part of the `nftables` project).

Usage Instructions

Before deployment, a new traffic profile CR needs to be created and configured. Traffic control in k8s-netem is provided by one of several modular controllers, one of which can be selected for each traffic profile. Two controllers are currently implemented:

- “Builtin” which uses the `tc` command provided by the `iproute2` userspace utilities to configure the Linux Traffic Control (TC) subsystem to which the built-in controller adds queuing disciplines and filters, and
- “Flexe” which is likewise based on `iproute2` and `tc` but adds additional functionality over the built-in controller.

The following is an example of a traffic profile for the Builtin controller:

```
1 apiVersion: k8s-netem.riasc.eu/v1
2 kind: TrafficProfile
3 metadata:
4   name: profile-builtin
5 spec:
6   podSelector:
7     matchLabels:
8       traffic-profile: builtin
9
10  type: Builtin
11  parameters:
12    netem:
13      delay: 0.2 # seconds
14      loss_ratio: 0.2 # in [0, 1]
15
16  egress:
17    - to:
18      - ipBlock:
19          cidr: 1.1.1.1/32
20      - podSelector:
21          matchLabels:
```

²⁵<https://github.com/ERIGrid2/k8s-netem>

```
22     component: example
23
24     inetProtos:
25     - icmp
```

In the next step, one or more pods need to be created which match the `podSelector` key of the traffic profile:

```
1  apiVersion: v1
2  kind: Pod
3  metadata:
4    labels:
5      component: example
6      traffic-profile: builtin
7    name: example-pod-1
8  spec:
9    containers:
10   - command:
11     - ping
12     - 1.1.1.1
13     image: nicolaka/netshoot
14     name: ping-cloudflare
15     securityContext:
16       capabilities:
17         add:
18         - NET_ADMIN
```

k8s-netem can be deployed by a dedicated Helm chart which can be found at the projects' related GitHub page²⁶.

A mutating admission webhook will inject a sidecar container into the newly created pods. The webhook gets invoked by the Kubernetes API server for each created, modified or deleted pod resource.

Once deployed, the sidecar container will configure the network traffic controller by detecting new or modified traffic profiles matching the `podSelector` specification as well as new or modified pods which match the `podSelector` specification of ingress or egress peers. For new pods targeted by existing traffic profiles, an additional sidecar container will be injected into the pod.²⁷

The sidecar container will run alongside the user containers for the full life cycle of the pod. It is tasked with the synchronisation of traffic profiles with the Kernel TC/IPset data structures. As a result, modifications of existing traffic profiles by the user (e.g. to adjust impairment parameters) are synchronised to the Linux kernel configuration.

Further documentation can be found at the related web page²⁸.

²⁶<https://github.com/ERIGrid2/charts/tree/master/charts/netem>

²⁷*Note:* Currently, the webhook will only inject the sidecar if the traffic profile already exists at the time of pod creation or update; k8s-netem will not re-create pods after a new traffic profile is added to the cluster.

²⁸<https://riasc.eu/docs/design/network-emulation>

4 Conclusions

This report serves as a guide and documentation for the software and other machine-consumable outcomes of ERIGrid 2.0's JRA 2. It encompasses simulation models, code examples that demonstrate PoC, and deployable tools. The purpose of this document is to provide instructions and information without duplicating the methodical and technical background already covered in the previous Deliverable D11.1 (*D-JRA2.1 Coupling Methods, 2023*). Thus, it should be used alongside this report. In cases where a technical background is presented in this document, the focus is primarily set on implementation considerations.

The report covered software releases related to co-simulation, time benchmark, distributed RI experiments framework, mesh peer-to-peer connections, and communication network emulator. Several of these releases are planned to be used in the demonstration activities later on in ERIGrid 2.0 and are to this end being developed further. Therefore, this document at hand can only provide a snapshot of the results as far as activities of JRA 2 are concerned.

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